

Book chapter title - "Social justice and sustainability in higher education "

Sushant Thakur

Assisant Professor Department English Govt Model Residential College Jawanga
Geedam Dantewada Chhattisagrh

Corresponding author- **Sushant Thakur**

Email - Sushant.2521@Gmail.Com

Abstract

Education is the first fundamental sector which establish inclusive environment for people and make them aware about rights, and justice. But our regional, socio culture and socio economic differences engulf the sector of higher education and created education exclusion in the higher education field. Social justice and sustainability is a essential component of education but disparities and gaps had been festering the opportunity of the minorities, tribes and backward class students .a nation without inclusion and equity, similar access to recourses cannot be alive in peace and development with harmony. We have to prepare a framework & solid roadmap to eradicate exclusion and social injustice in higher education and firmly we have to ensure the regulation and systematic monitoring of the education policy followed in the institutions or universities.

Keywords: equity, inclusion, higher education, gaps, disparities

Introduction

We are a social animal and we exist in society form decades but yet we have created so many gaps and differences on the name of rituals, region and socioeconomic subjects. The world is transforming into a new form in many ways and getting united on global platform to achieve sustainable development goals for mankind but equity and inclusion are key element that needs to be added in roots of system & society so that it can bear the fruits of peace and prosperity in whole world. The problem of education exclusion is still prevailing in our system. The concept of social justice has been introduced in our education system by UGC norms but still we are severely facing the challenge of inequity.

Objectives

To understand the concept of social justice and its expansion to the mankind and education. Role of the social justice in the overall development of the students of higher education. Need of the equity and inclusive education in all perspectives. Understanding the Barriers and obstacles in brining the social justice in higher education institutions. Efforts and scheme by the govt and administration to check the exclusion in education.

Methodology

By observation study and the use of the both quantitative and qualitative method in the campus of the higher education institutions. Survey has done among the students.

Understanding Social Justice

Social justice simply refers to equal access to resources, opportunities, education, social rights & privileges in a society. It also refereed as distributive justice which brings a political, social fairness and equality for individual being. Social justice as a strong theory make stronger emphasis on human rights and now its mandatory tool to improve the lives of backward, exploited disadvantaged,

minority and vulnerable groups facing discrimination in society either on the basis of gender, race, religion or economically.

Expansion of the Social justice concept in higher education

For a long time period Social justice was treated as a subject matter for financial and e economic distress ,gaps and inequality but later by privatization and globalization industrialization ,social media revolution transformed the concept of the social justice completely. Now it focuses on the key words inclusion. Inclusion is a broad term which represents sex, environment, race, gender, ethnicity, heritage, social status, religion based fairness and equity. Hence at preset era the measure of social justice covers the all major human dimension in universal way for better treatment, access, and inclusion.

India has been emerging as a power hub for the youth all over the world we have largest youth man power working and studying but these vast youth generation came across from the various state and with differences & diversity in culture, races, gender language and other forms. This generates challenges of inequity and exclusion. In the present era education sector is the fastest growing sector in the world, even in our country UGC has initiated so many higher education institution but even though providing equal education to most rural population and the backward groups is a biggest challenge. The higher education sector is facing the challenge to incorporate social inclusion into their curricula and HEIs and established a roadmap to provide more flexible and accessible educational opportunities to students. UGC has created a frame work for inclusive education which is mandatory to follow by the all HEIs and universities .In the NAAC ACCREDITION criteria 7 the institution or university has to submit the report to UGC regarding the initiative applied and followed for the social

inclusion and equity. To support the inclusive National Education Policy 2020 has been announced in our country to bring various reforms in school education as well as higher education with the aim for equity inclusive and equitable education for all. The New Education Policy is designed in keeping the point of social justice and eradicate gaps in education system. The key initiative of the national education policy 2020 is :- Promote language inclusion by giving priority to the education in mother tongue and availability of the content for the students in the local dialects and language.

Launch of new scheme and policy for socially and Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs) To support the marginalized and below poverty line students students scholarship scheme has been launched. Making strict policy for gender inclusion and creating awareness program for gender sensitization Reservation for tribal and particularly vulnerable group and minority class people has been announced for admission and fees. Physically challenged students have now right to free education and equal access.

Implementing social justice in higher education & challenges

We must need to update the education system despite of the following challenges-

Gender inequality and gender gap in India -

Accessibility, equity, quality and Gender neutral – these are the key feature of the education. In last few decades to promote girl education & gender sensitization the Indian government has launched a plenty of schemes and initiatives to promote education among girl & women empowerment. Some major successful key initiative are beti bachao beti padhao scheme,suknkya samdrdhi yojna,working women hostel,suchita – sanitary & hygiene scheme for higher education girls, girl scholarship schemes etc. these scheme emerge out as a game changer in the political social and economic perspective for girls.

The gross enrolment ratio of girls has a been increased in higher education and either in technical ,medical ,education ,media or political level footprints of girls has chalked a mark of success in every field. As per the report of the ministry of higher education and PIB(press information bureau) of India- The enrolment of girl in higher education has been increased in 2022 and girl enrolment percentage is now 49 percent in our country the Gender Parity Index (GPI) is 1.05 has been also increased.

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Table B.3: Gross Enrolment Ratio (per cent)

States/UTs	2021-22									2020-21		
	Elementary Schools (I-VIII)			Secondary Schools (IX-X)			Sr. Secondary Schools (XI-XII)			Higher Education (18-23 years age group)		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
D & N Haveli Daman & Diu	87.8	92.0	89.8	71.9	79.0	75.0	44.7	50.8	54.9	7.9	13.6	10.4
Delhi	118.3	124.5	121.3	110.3	112.2	111.2	91.2	99.5	94.9	46.7	48.5	47.6
Goa	80.4	93.0	91.1	80.6	85.7	83.0	71.2	76.3	73.7	30.8	37.3	33.8
Lakshadweep	75.4	71.1	73.2	64.7	61.9	63.3	64.9	60.0	62.4	3.3	11.4	7.2
Puducherry	76.4	77.7	77.0	73.4	79.1	76.1	64.6	71.1	68.7	60.3	61.1	60.8
All India	89.3	101.1	100.1	78.7	79.4	79.6	67.0	68.2	67.6	26.7	27.9	27.3

Source: Unified District Information System for Education (UDISE)+ 2021-22, Department of School Education & Literacy and All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) 2020-21

As per the report of the economic survey 2023 the India has made consistent progress and achieved the score value of only 0.490 in the gender inequality index but the HDI (human development index) 2023 of India reveals the inequality and gender disparities in our country.

The socio economic and socio culture of India is also a key factors which is causing the gender disparities in various form specially Higher education is the major sector where the gender

inequalities is still prevailing .the key causes for the gender gap and gender inequality are -

1. The social system of India is traditional and male dominant society even in present era that’s why it’s creating gender exclusion in the higher education of our country. Economically weak families are generally large and they cannot prefer to educate each and every children .they prefers male education over the girl education.
2. The condition varies from urban to rural areas in addition to it the gender gap conditions also

varies from one state to another .In the rural areas the girls' gross enrollment ratio is still lagging far behind as compared to urban region. A traditional role expectation for girls is limited in rural area so they don't allow them to go outside the skirt of village for higher education.

3. Availability of resources for higher education in nearby.UGC has established HEIs in large numbers and state govt are also making effort to provide the higher education easily accessible and approachable for girls. Remote and tribal girls have to visit more than 50 kms for quality education so due to remote access they ought to drop out each year.

Linguistic Inclusion:

Language barriers are a major issue that causes education exclusion. Even in now a day's language barriers is a key obstacle for students specially it impacts the higher education sector. In higher education sector the student came across from different state in universities or colleges. India is country of versatility and diversity in language and culture. Different dialects and various languages are spoken in each state. In so many states the medium of instruction for teaching is the local dialects and local language in the schools so the students of such schools have not well & enough command over the key language like English. It affects the students when they visit to universities or college for further higher studies. After independence the numbers of school and college have been consistently increasing but the number of Hindi medium school has been established more as compared to English medium schools .a large numbers of students complete their school education in local language or Hindi medium. They face severe difficulty to cop up with the other students in higher education. Medical, engineering, aeronautics, information technology or deference sectors these sectors primary requirement is god command over the English language. The high dropout rate in higher education is also the language barrier .in a tough competitive world so many students are lagging behind just because of the language exclusion. We need to ensure the design the curriculum and availability of the study material in the all the major language so that it can reach up to all students it will provide the equity and equal access to all open resource and brings social justice in our education society.

Great Initiative -We can look over the example of the Madhya Pradesh state where they initiated the Medical study in the Hindi medium so the students can over come from the barriers of the language barrier and a healthy competitive environment will be established al over the state. We need restructuring and updation in the higher education model to avoid educational exclusion.

Regional Inclusion India has huge diversity in regional level and it's a mammoth challenge to overcome from this issue to bring inclusion. Especially it becomes very difficult for the students from different region to survive when they take admission for higher education in universities.

In cultural and social way it's a crucial task to mingle up with other students with geographical and cultural differences.. To promote regional inclusion central govt has started Conduct of NEET and other central examinations under the NTA (National testing agency).For every states students only one entrance examination will be conducted for medical entrance .It will provide a healthy and equal opportunity for students without the barriers of region & geographical differences.

Allocation of Scholarship in state and central collaboration as per regional inclusion

Third language teaching has been started in central govt schools so that students will be familiar and learn the third culture language in their curriculum. In jawahar navodya vidyalaya student can opt for one year migration and they can study for 9th class in other state for one year

Inclusion of the students with benchmark disabilities

Education always gives strength to the Persons with Disabilities and it's the only power for the physically challenged students by which they can become self depend and change their lives.

Our constitution has declared the right to Education for such students so that they not only become Skilled but also serve the nation and society. Its mandatory for all HEIs to make supportive infrastructure in the campus for the physically challenged students and provide the learning equipments in the campus. Pre metric and post metric scholarships are available for the physically disabled students type of the physical disability has been benchmarked for the students to gain the benefit provided by the govt.

Recommendation & Conclusion-

However, despite the growing number of institutions, one of the biggest challenges is providing access and equity to quality higher education to a diverse population. But to provide social justice to students Rashtriya Uchchatar Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA) and the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) has been established by govt. In addition to it e-learning platforms is being developed to make higher education more accessible and affordable for all.

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